

PERCEPTIONS

Migration to the EU:
Best practices and ICT tools in migration-related work:
a survey of first-line practitioners

Table of Content

3		Authors
4		The PERCEPTIONS Project
6		Executive Summary
8	1.	Introduction
8	1.1.	Aims and design of the survey
15	1.2.	Survey distribution and data collection
16	1.3	Issues with recruitment
18	2.	Description of the sample and methodology
18	2.1	The sample obtained
25	2.2	A note on methodology
26	3.	Main results
27	Theme 1:	Migration-related issues on which first-line practitioners work, and activities they employ in their work on these issues
32	Theme 2:	Practitioners' assessments of the potential success of activities to address misinformation amongst migrants
37	Theme 3:	Practitioners' assessment of criteria through which to evaluate the success of activities in migration-related work.
38	Theme 4:	Practitioners' use and assessment of ICT tools in migration-related work
47	4.	Conclusions and discussion
49		Limitations of the survey, and questions for future research
50		References
52		Annex 1: Survey questionnaire
65		Annex 1: Survey questionnaire

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PERCEPTIONS

The PERCEPTIONS Project

The Horizon 2020 project **PERCEPTIONS** identifies images of and perceptions about the EU held outside Europe and examines the way they influence migration decisions. It further aims to understand how such perceptions are distributed via various channels, how the flow of information could be distorted, and whether inaccurate information could lead to threats to the security of migrants (e.g. through dangerous border crossings) or national security (e.g. radicalisation).

PROJECT OBJECTIVES: The main objectives of the three-year project are (1) to identify narratives, images and perceptions of Europe abroad, (2) to investigate how different narratives could lead to unrealistic expectations, problems and security threats for host societies as well as migrants and in what way; and (3) to create toolkits using creative and innovative measures to react or even counteract them, considering social, societal and structural aspects.

CONSORTIUM: The project involves 25 partners in 15 countries. These countries include 12 European countries and four non-European countries (Algeria, Egypt, Tunisia, and Israel). The project runs from September 2019 to February 2023.

Consortium

SYNYO GmbH (SYNYO), Austria

Sheffield Hallam University (CENTRIC), UK

Alma Mater Studiorum Universita di Bologna (UNIBO), Italy

University of Granada (UGR), Spain

University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC), Spain

University of Northumbria at Newcastle (UNN), UK

Swansea University (SU), UK

University of Rome La Sapienza (SAPIENZA), Italy

Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR), Netherlands

University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN), Belgium

International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD), Austria

Kentro Meleton Asfaleias - Center for Security Studies (KEMEA), Greece

Center for the Study of Democracy (CSD), Bulgaria

SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (SINUS), Germany

Centre de Recherche en Economie Appliquée pour le Développement (CREAD), Algeria

Egyptian Center for Innovation and Technology Development (ECITD), Egypt

ADITESS Advanced Integrated Technology Solutions & Services LTD (ADITESS), Cyprus

Association of Local Democracy Agencies (ALDA), France

Kosovar Centre for Security Studies (KCSS), Kosovo

Euro-Arab Foundation for Higher Studies (FUNDEA), Spain

Koinonia Caritas Cyprus (CARITAS), Cyprus

Fondazione Bruno Kessler (FBK), Italy

Hellenic Police (HP), Greece

Ministry of Public Security - Israel National Police (MOPS-INP), Israel

Ministry of Interior - Chief Directorate Border Police (CDBP), Bulgaria

Centre of Excellence in Terrorism, Resilience, Intelligence and Organised Crime Research (CENTRIC), UK

Contact

Executive Summary

This report presents results from a survey with first-line practitioners working in areas related to migration. The survey was available in 10 languages (Albanian, Arabic, Bulgarian, Dutch, English, French, German, Greek, Italian, and Spanish) and was open between the 2nd of March and the 19th of April, 2022.

The survey aimed to investigate practitioners' assessments of best practices in migration-related work. More specifically, practitioners were asked to share their attitudes toward potential strategies for addressing the issue of misinformation amongst migrants and criteria through which to assess the success of potential best practices, as well as their evaluations of existing Information Communication Technology (ICT) tools in migration-related work.

The survey received 755 valid responses, with a large number of responses from female, European practitioners working in support services.

Key results from the survey, discussed in more detail in the sections that follow, include:

- At the time the survey was carried out, the majority of practitioners reported that their organisations were still moderately to severely impacted by COVID-19 pandemic.
- Practitioners considered various types of face-to-face engagement (with migrant individuals or communities, and with other professionals) to be the most successful activities to address misinformation amongst migrants.
- In contrast, practitioners viewed online engagement with migrants and arts- and culture-based activities as the least successful means of addressing misinformation amongst migrants.
- Irrespective of their fields of work, as well as whether they were from EU or non-EU countries, practitioners assessed protection of human rights as the most important criteria for evaluating the success of practices in migration-related work.
- In contrast, and also irrespective of their field of work, practitioners assessed transferability as the least important criteria to evaluate the success of a potential best practice.
- A plurality of practitioners identified the intended beneficiaries' own involvement in an activity and the beneficiaries' satisfaction with and gain from the activity as additional criteria through which to evaluate the activity's success.
- The majority of practitioners in the survey used ICT tools for accessing data on migration and for education and training purposes.

- Practitioners generally considered existing ICT tools in migration-related work to be effective, user-friendly, and understandable. This was especially true for ICT tools that practitioners used to share guidelines with other practitioners/stakeholders and to share information with migrants.
- Practitioners working on raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration and monitoring media representations of migrants tended to offer especially positive evaluations of existing ICT tools.

Section 1:

Introduction

The first section of this report provides an overview of the aims of the survey, in the context of the PERCEPTIONS project. It also details the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the survey and survey distribution by country and by language. Finally, it highlights key issues faced during the recruitment period.

1.1. Aims and design of the survey

As stated in the introduction to the first iteration of the PERCEPTIONS survey (García-Carmona et al., 2021a), first-line practitioners have been identified as an under-researched group in migration studies (Bayerl et al., 2020), yet one able to provide key insights with regard to professional attitudes and practices – both of which have an impact on migration governance, as well as on migrants themselves.

The first iteration of the survey (García-Carmona et al., 2021a) focused on attitudes: specifically, it investigated first-line practitioners' ideas about migration, their attribution of (positive vs. negative and accurate vs. inaccurate¹) perceptions of Europe to migrants, and their identification of any threats connected to these perceptions.

The second iteration of the survey shifted the focus to practices: specifically, first-line practitioners' assessment of best practices in migration-related work, with a particular focus on assessment of best practices to address misinformation amongst migrants, which has been identified as a particularly important line of research by the PERCEPTIONS project (Bayerl et al., 2020, pp. 31). The survey also included questions on the use of Information Communication Technology (ICT) tools in work with migrants, as well as on practitioners' sectors of work, level of professional contact with recently-arrived migrants, and socio-demographic attributes. A question on the impact of COVID-19 on practitioners' work was also included, to provide comparability with iteration I. Finally, the survey included an optional section on workplace psychology and intercultural competence.

¹ In the PERCEPTIONS project, we refrain from judging whether migrants' perceptions (of Europe, the EU, a European country) are accurate or inaccurate, as perceptions are inherently subjective. The survey, however, intended to capture the way practitioners ascribe correctness and incorrectness to migrants' perceptions.

The full set of research questions addressed by the first and second iterations are as follows:

Question	Iteration
What role do first-line practitioners believe migrants' perceptions of Europe play in their mobility decisions?	1
What perceptions of Europe and the target countries do first-line practitioners ascribe to migrants?	1
Do first-line practitioners assess migrants' perceptions of various aspects of life in Europe as accurate or inaccurate?	1
In the view of first-line practitioners, do certain inaccurate perceptions and narratives about Europe lead directly or indirectly to security threats?	1
In what ways do first-line practitioners believe COVID-19 has affected migrant perceptions?	1
Do first-line practitioners view their organisations' work with migrants as effective?	1
Are first-line practitioners satisfied with their working conditions and European migration policies?	1
Has the COVID-19 pandemic affected first-line practitioners' life and job satisfaction?	1
Has the COVID-19 pandemic affected first-line practitioners' perceived organisational effectiveness?	1 & 2
On what migration-related issues do first-line practitioners currently work, and what types of activities do they employ in their work on these issues?	2
How successful do first-line practitioners believe different types of activities can be in work on different migration-related issues?	2
How successful do first-line practitioners believe different types of activities can be in addressing misinformation among migrants?	2
What criteria do first-line practitioners believe should be used when evaluating the success of activities in migration-related work?	2
How do first-line practitioners currently use ICT tools in their work on migration?	2
How do first-line practitioners assess current ICT tools in their fields of work?	2

Table 1. Research questions

In order to minimise the time burden on respondents, the second iteration survey questionnaire was limited to seven modules: A. Professional information (5 questions); B. COVID-19 and professional life (1 question); C. Practitioner contact with migrants (1 question); D. Promising practices in migration-related work (5 questions); E. ICT tools in migration-related work (3 questions); F. Socio-demographic information (4 questions); G. Optional: intercultural competences and training in migration-related work (6 questions).

The design of key survey questions and answer items was based upon the desk research conducted in PERCEPTIONS work packages (WPs) 2 and 5, as well as the qualitative interviews conducted with practitioners and policymakers in WP3. Specifically, Module D on promising practices in migration-related work adapted the typology of “best practice categories” identified in WP5 of the PERCEPTIONS project (Spathi et al., 2021, pp. 16-17). The typology was adapted in the following manner in order to reduce redundancy, fill gaps identified in the qualitative research, and improve comprehension for respondents unfamiliar with the project’s prior work:

Category and #, Spathi et al. (2021)	Item, Spathi et al. (2021)	Item, survey questionnaire
Best practices: BP1	Addressing negative public perceptions, racism, and xenophobia towards migrants in the host country	Countering and preventing discrimination against migrants in host countries
Best practices: BP2	Awareness raising on the migrant journey and the risks associated with irregular migration routes (human trafficking, migrant smuggling, deaths, etc.) along with policies to tackle them	Raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration
		Raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries
Best practices: BP3	Migrant integration in the host country (education, labour, housing, cultural integration)	Migrant integration in host countries
Best practices: BP4	Migrants reintegration to country of origin	Migrant reintegration in countries of origin
Best practices: BP5	Protection of human rights of migrants and protection against other threats related to them in the host country (policies)	Protection of migrants' human rights

Best practices: BP6	Review of media representations of migrants and other fake news	Monitoring media representations of migrants
		Countering misinformation among migrants (about conditions along migration routes, in host countries, etc.)
Best practices: BP7	Tackling radicalisation, hate speech, extremist behaviours and/or terrorism	Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants
		Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants
Best practices: BP8	Countering border-related crime	Countering organised border crime (e.g., human trafficking, migrant smuggling, etc.)
		Countering irregular border crossing

Table 2. Adaptation of best practice items from Spathi et al. (2021)

During the survey, once respondents had specified best practices categories relevant to their work, they were asked whether their organisation had conducted any specific types of activities within these categories. The typology of activities was based on the “general threats and countermeasures” identified by Spathi et al. (2021, pp. 17), adapted in the following manner in order to improve comprehensibility for respondents unfamiliar with the project’s prior work:

Category and #, Spathi et al. (2021)	Item, Spathi et al. (2021)	Item, survey questionnaire
General threats and countermeasures: GTC1	Community related (social networking, collaboration schemes, peer-to-peer meetings with community, neighbourhood activities etc.)	Face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities (counselling, neighbourhood workshops, peer-to-peer activities, etc.)
General threats and countermeasures: GTC2	ICT related (online interactive platforms, mobile applications, digital portfolios)	Online engagement with migrant individuals or communities (counselling, social media campaigns, mobile apps, etc.)
General threats and countermeasures: GTC3	Legal based (code of practices, existing policies, social and legal assistance, legislature)	Policy work (drafting laws and regulations, policy guidelines, codes of conduct, etc.)
General threats and countermeasures: GTC4	Recommendations lists, reports, factsheets, and academic studies.	Media activities for the general public (print media, online, TV, radio, etc.) countries of origin
		Media activities for a specialist audience (white papers, guidelines, expert podcasts, etc.)
General threats and countermeasures: GTC5	Social Media and Art-based (exhibitions, recreational and cultural activities, photo galleries, festivals, cinema screenings, theatre, tv reports, video/media clips etc.)	Arts and culture-based activities (exhibitions, performances, festivals, etc.)
General threats and countermeasures: GTC6	Workshops, conferences, forums, educational and training sessions, awareness campaigns and dedicated manuals and handbooks + e-learnings	Face-to-face engagement with other professionals (seminars, trainings, etc.)
		Online engagement with other professionals (webinars, e-learning/training, etc.)

Table 3. Adaptation of activity items from Spathi et al. (2021)

After assessing the potential effectiveness of these types of activities, the respondents were asked to rank the importance of criteria commonly used to evaluate the success of such activities; the five criteria were adapted from the five “qualifier criteria” used by Spathi et al. (2021, p. 25):

Category and #, Spathi et al. (2021)	Item, Spathi et al. (2021)	Item, survey questionnaire
Qualifier criteria: QC1	Impact	Overall impact
Qualifier criteria: QC2	Protection of rights	Protection of human rights (e.g., of migrants and other target groups)
Qualifier criteria: QC3	Sustainability	Sustainability (i.e., can the activity be maintained/ implemented over time?)
Qualifier criteria: QC4	Transferability	Transferability (i.e., can the activity be transferred to other sites and contexts?)
Qualifier criteria: QC5	Intersectoral coordination	Intersectoral coordination (i.e., does the activity effectively involve multiple groups of stakeholders?)

Table 4. Adaptation of qualifier criteria from Spathi et al. (2021)

In the PERCEPTIONS project, Spathi et al. (2021), used the “resistance to change” method with seven partner organisations to assign weights to each of these qualifier criteria, which were then used in a weighted evaluation of the best practices collected by the various partners (pp. 22-27). When designing the survey, it was anticipated that first-line practitioners in the field might prioritise different criteria than the PERCEPTIONS project partners.

All revised typologies were checked and revised iteratively by a group of PERCEPTIONS partner organisations prior to being integrated into the final survey questionnaire.

Additional ICT-related questions were designed with researchers from the project partner Fondazione Bruno Kessler. These questions were designed to identify positive and negative aspects of existing ICT solutions to take into account in the design and implementation of similar solutions in the PERCEPTIONS project (see Deppieri & Mana, 2022).

Finally: like the first iteration, the second iteration included several questions with open response boxes in which participants could write extra explanations for their answers, or extra information they considered relevant (five in total). All questions were deemed non-sensitive and capable of being safely answered by participants in both EU and non-EU countries; accordingly, region-specific dependency pathways were not programmed.

In addition to the survey questionnaire itself, participants were provided with a disclaimer on the survey landing page in which they were informed, in their language, about their rights with regards to data protection and withdrawing responses.

1.2. Survey distribution and data collection

The survey was open between the 2nd of March and the 19th of April, 2022. As in the first iteration (see García-Carmona et al., 2021a), the survey was distributed in the following countries across and beyond Europe:

Austria	Germany
Belgium	Greece
Bulgaria	Italy
Cyprus	Spain
Egypt	The Netherlands
France	The United Kingdom

To engage with practitioners across these countries, the survey was available in 10 different languages:

Albanian	French
Arabic	German
Bulgarian	Greek
Dutch	Italian
English	Spanish

The inclusion criteria for the survey were very broad, including but not limited to the following profiles of first-line practitioners: border security experts; border security policymakers; border security officers and authorities; coast guard officers and authorities; law enforcement agency officers and authorities; law enforcement policymakers; governmental and non-governmental health organisations; governmental and non-governmental welfare organisations; governmental and non-governmental youth and child service organisations; migrant advocacy organisations; legal aid organisations; housing providers and housing assistance organisations; faith-based organisations and faith-based communities.

All participation in the survey was completely voluntary, and participants were free to stop answering the survey at any time. Participants also had to give their informed consent and confirm that they were over 18 before answering survey questions. Minors were therefore not included in the survey sample.

1.3 Issues with recruitment

In response to the lower-than-expected response rate in several target countries during the first iteration of the survey, efforts were made to reduce barriers to participation. In order to hold the survey length under ten minutes total, the introduction was streamlined; the number of modules and questions per module were minimised; and an effort was made to use simple, everyday language throughout the original draft and translations alike.

A target number of 40 responses per country was met in the following field-sites: Austria, Cyprus, Bulgaria, Greece, Italy and Spain. Responses were also high in Algeria (39), Belgium (33) and the UK (37). However, despite the mitigation measures taken, responses in Egypt (8), France (0), Germany (16), Kosovo (7) and the Netherlands (17) were low.

In addition, there were 489 incomplete responses at the time of closing the survey (an attrition rate of 39%). A handful of participants reported to the recruiting organisations that they found the questionnaire either irrelevant to their professional experience or difficult to understand, which are potential grounds for attrition. Other potential grounds for attrition include having reached a “curiosity plateau” at the beginning of the survey, after which attention tends to wander; it is plausible that this problem could especially affect respondents taking a survey at work (Eysenbach, 2005). However, survey attrition remains an understudied phenomenon in non-biomedical social science.

There were several additional factors that impacted recruitment at the consortium level.

First, the overlapping crises of the COVID-19 pandemic and the Ukraine emergency resulted in difficulties contacting first-line practitioners, who were overburdened, and a general sense of survey fatigue amongst potential participants. For example, although some partners commented that the Russian war against Ukraine and resulting humanitarian crisis did not dramatically influence recruitment, many noted that it left first-line practitioners with little time and resources to allocate to voluntary participation in research. For several partners, the crisis also caused backlogs in communication with potential participants and delays in filling out the survey. This being said, partners in Bulgaria noted that the crisis actually resulted in increased engagement from participants, as researchers convinced them of the importance of sharing their views at such a challenging moment.

In addition to the crises, some partners noted that it was very difficult to compete for first-line practitioners’ attention with multiple EU and non-EU funded projects simultaneously working to investigate the same issues. Another factor at the organisational level that impacted recruitment in several countries was the fact that the time required for the survey to filter through institutions or to gain institutional approval was not enough. On reflection, these partners noted that an extension of the survey could have yielded increased results.

In terms of more localised impacts on recruitment, notable events or factors included the following:

- In Kosovo, allegations of corruption and organised crime amongst police in customs significantly impacted the target population availability and willingness to participate in the survey.
- In Egypt, potential participants were reluctant to fill out the survey prior to the country's new law on data protection and privacy being passed (it was expected to be passed in April 2022).
- In France, the presidential campaign, which saturated social media with migration-related articles and comments, made it difficult for potential participants to find their way to the survey.
- In Belgium and France, recruitment coincided with a two-week Easter holiday (4th-18th of April).
- In Germany, there were anecdotal indications of hesitation among governmental stakeholders to take part in research on politically sensitive issues, especially in the wake of the COVID-19 and Ukraine crises – even under conditions of anonymity.
- In the Netherlands, there were reported difficulties with survey-based research in general. Partners commented that response rates to survey research in the Netherlands tend to be notoriously low.
- In the UK, partners reported difficulties with organisational capacity in general, as relevant organisations there tend to be very small, with limited human resources to take part in a survey.

Section 2:

Description of the sample and methodology

This section gives an overview of the sample of first-line practitioners who participated in the survey. It includes socio-demographic information like age, gender and languages spoken, highest level of education completed, as well as a range of professional information: the countries, organisations, and levels in which practitioners work; years of experience in the field; the responsibility they had for supervising the work of other employees; and the most common profiles of the migrants with whom they work.

2.1 The sample obtained

The survey received 755 valid responses. This sample included practitioners working in a varied spectrum of countries. However, it should be noted that there were a very low number of responses from certain countries

and a large number of responses from others (see Figure 1). The results are thus biased towards the views of practitioners working in the countries most represented.

A2. In what country do you work?

Figure 1. Countries in which practitioners worked

To facilitate analysis, the countries listed above were grouped into two categories: on the one hand, all those in geographic Europe (93.6%), labelled as EU countries, and on the other hand, the African countries (Algeria, Egypt and Tunisia; 6.4%), labelled as non-EU countries. Figure 2 shows the number of responses received per group.

Figure 2. Grouped countries in which practitioners work

First-line practitioners’ organisations operated in a wide range of sectors, from women’s services to border and customs enforcement. For analytical purposes, these sectors of work were also grouped into larger categories. The first group (labelled “Enforcement agencies and policymaking”, 14.2%) included sectors more related to security, border control, and governmental functions of a diplomatic and political nature, whilst the second group (labelled “Support services”, 78.3%) included different sectors related to support for immigrants. The third group (labelled “Other”, 7.5%) included all sectors that did not fit into the first two categories². Open responses received to the question on practitioners’ sectors of work made reference to organisations that could have been included in the previous categories, for example child protection, asylum services or social assistance. The distribution of respondents between the groups was unbalanced, with 14.2% in group 1 and 78.3% in group 2.

² Group 1 includes the following sectors: border enforcement, customs enforcement, and internal law enforcement; and diplomatic, governance and policymaking. Group 2 includes organisations that carry out support work: diplomatic and legal aid, judiciary, etc.; immigration and asylum services, and judiciary and legal services, youth work women’s services child services and education or VET, psychological and health services, housing services, immigrant advocacy.

A1. Do you work for a non-governmental, governmental or intergovernmental organisation?

A5. In what sectors does your organisation primarily operate?

Figure 3. Types of organisation in which practitioners worked and sectors in which organisations operated

First-line practitioners surveyed worked in organisations operating at a range of different levels of governance: intergovernmental, governmental, non-governmental, and other. There was a clear predominance of governmental organisations and non-faith based non-governmental organisations. In addition, 145 respondents selected the option “Other”, reporting in an open response box that they worked for a range of organisations, from private companies (57 responses) to academic institutions (2 responses) or freelance professions (17 responses, e.g., lawyers).

Participants were also asked about the administrative levels at which their entities operated (local-communal, federal-national, international, state-prefectural, other). As Figure 3 shows, most respondents indicated that their organisation worked at the national level.

Figure 4. Level at which practitioners' organisations worked

In terms of gender, 476 (62.3%) respondents were women, and 253 were men (33.3%).

78.5% of participants were between the age of 30 and 59 years old. In the sample, 96 respondents were between 20 and 29 years old, and 46 were over 60.

In general terms, the educational level of the first-line practitioners surveyed was very high. All respondents, except one, had completed at least secondary education, vocational training, or a professional certificate. In addition, 90.6% of respondents held a bachelor's degree, master's degree, or PhD.

In the sample, a high percentage of practitioners, 66%, reported having frequent contact with migrants (defined as contact several times a month or more) prior to the COVID-19 pandemic, with a plurality of practitioners (31%) reporting daily contact.

It should be noted that neither iteration of the survey aimed to generate representative data on the target population of "practitioners who work with migrants and/or on migration-related issues". Doing so would not be possible, as the parameters of this population are not known. For instance, while the survey sample is imbalanced with regard to gender, the gender ratio of the target population may well also be imbalanced; it is indeterminable whether the sample accurately reflects the target population or not. Accordingly, the data should be interpreted as exploratory. Nevertheless, the authors believe that the generalities and differences discovered can be prudently extrapolated to different national contexts against the backdrop of careful desk research (and preferably also additional empirical research) on these contexts.

COVID-19

Practitioners were also asked to assess the degree to which the COVID-19 pandemic had affected their organisations' operations and were given a Likert scale on which 0 was "not affected at all" and 7 was "very severely affected".

As Figure 5 shows, the majority of respondents indicated that, since December 2020, the pandemic had continued to impact their work, with values of 5, 6, and 7 accounting for 65.87% of all responses. In the first iteration of the survey, 67.3% of respondents marked 6 or above. A comparison of the results therefore suggests that while the impact of the pandemic has remained significant, it lessened slightly in the period between the first and second iterations.

B1. Thinking of the period between December 2020 and now, how severely has the pandemic affected your organisation's operations?

Figure 5. The degree to which practitioners' organisations had been affected by COVID-19

In a similar vein, Figure 6 shows that COVID-19 affected respondents in EU countries and non-EU countries to a similar degree. However, the percentage of non-EU country respondents claiming that COVID-19 had hardly affected their organisations' operations is significant.

B1. Thinking of the period between December 2020 and now, how severely has the pandemic affected your organisation's operations?

Figure 6. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on practitioners in EU and non-EU countries

All types of organisations for which practitioners worked had been affected by the pandemic: however, the impact does appear to have been most severe on support services. For example, as Figure 7 shows, for all organisations, the majority of responses were concentrated between 5-7. For "enforcement agencies & policymaking", 53.82% of practitioners' responses fell within this range, for "other", 63.16%, and for "support services" 68.26%.

B1. Thinking of the period between December 2020 and now, how severely has the pandemic affected your organisation's operations?

Figure 7. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on practitioners in different sectors

2.2 A note on methodology

A range of statistical techniques were employed to analyse the results of the survey data. This section aims to provide a brief overview of the methodology and techniques used.

There are a wide range of variables in the dataset, and those most able to provide preliminary answers to the research questions (see table 1) were selected for analysis, with frequency tables and descriptive statistics created to present the outcomes. This approach was also used to observe trends in the distribution of frequencies that, on certain occasions, displayed a high deviation. When distributions of frequencies were polarised, the structure of these deviations was explored through statistical analyses, in which different variables were compared.

Most of the variables in the survey were qualitative. However, as they follow Likert scales, they were generally treated analytically as quantitative variables. Some qualitative variables were also used as grouping variables

in order to comparatively analyse organisations according to particular characteristics. The following were used as grouping variables: type of country (European country or non-European country), type of organisation (enforcement agencies or support services), and issue on which practitioners' organisations worked.

Responses to the open question D5 (Please specify the other criteria [through which to assess the success of activities in migration-related work]) were also analysed, using a type of content analysis (Bardin, 1996). The analysis first compared the 118 open responses to five given items in question D4 (overall impact, protection of human rights, sustainability, transferability, intersectorial coordination). Responses that did not fit within the five given criteria were then further analysed to identify other criteria through which to evaluate the success of activities in migration-related work.

Section 3:

Main results

This section details the main results of the survey. The results are organised around four themes, each of which is based on one or more of the research questions specified in section 1.

- Theme 1:** Migration-related issues on which first-line practitioners work, and activities they employ.
- Theme 2:** Practitioners' assessments of the potential success of activities to address misinformation amongst migrants.
- Theme 3:** Practitioners' assessment of criteria through which to evaluate the success of activities in migration-related work.
- Theme 4:** Practitioners' use and assessment of ICT tools in migration-related work.

Each theme opens with “key findings”, which are then explored in more detail. As well as presenting trends in the sample of first-line practitioners as a whole, the results focus on key differences between a range of groups of first-line practitioners. As mentioned in the methodology section, practitioners were grouped both by the type of country in which they were located (categorised as EU or non-EU countries), and the main issues on which their organisations worked.

Theme 1:

Migration-related issues on which first-line practitioners work, and activities they employ in their work on these issues

Research question:

On what migration-related issues do first-line practitioners currently work, and what types of activities do they employ in their work on these issues?

Key findings:

- In general, most practitioners in the sample worked for organisations focused on migrant integration in host countries and protection of migrants' human rights.
- Respondents from EU countries tended to work for organisations focused on migrant integration in host countries, protection of migrants' human rights, countering misinformation among migrants, and raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries.
- Respondents in countries outside the EU tended to work for organisations focused on countering organised border crime, countering irregular border crossing, raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration, and raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries.
- The activities first-line practitioners used most in their work were face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities and face-to-face engagement with other professionals.
- The activities practitioners used least were media activities for a specialist audience (white papers, guidelines, expert podcasts, etc.) and arts- and culture-based activities.

Practitioners were asked to specify the issues related to migration on which their organisation worked. They could select multiple choices from the following list of options:

- Raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration.
- Raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries.
- Countering misinformation among migrants (about conditions on migration routes, in host countries, etc.).
- Countering discrimination against migrants.
- Protection of migrants' human rights.
- Migrant integration in host countries.
- Migrant reintegration in countries of origin.
- Monitoring media representations of migrants.
- Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants.
- Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants.
- Countering organised border crime (e.g., human trafficking, migrant smuggling, etc.).
- Countering irregular border crossing.
- Other.

Table 5, below, presents an overview of the issues on which practitioners worked.

	Frequency	
	No	Yes
Raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration	575	180
Raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries	489	266
Countering misinformation among migrants	609	146
Countering misinformation among migrants	479	276
Protection of migrants' human rights	389	366

Migrant integration in host countries	335	420
Migrant reintegration in countries of origin	689	66
Monitoring media representations of migrants	661	94
Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants	610	145
Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants	685	70
Countering organised border crime	631	124
Countering irregular border crossing	646	109
Other	620	135

Table 5. Issues related to migration on which practitioners' organisations worked

As Table 5 illustrates, in general, practitioners' organisations tended to focus on "migrant integration in host countries" (n= 420) and "protection of migrants' human rights" (n= 366). However, there were some significant differences between the issues on which EU and non-EU-based practitioners most frequently worked.

The majority of practitioners from EU countries, for example, worked for organisations focused on the issue of "migrant integration in host countries" (n=410), followed by "protection of migrants' human rights" (n= 352), "countering misinformation among migrants" (n=271) and "raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries" (n= 253).

In contrast, practitioners in countries outside the EU tended to work for organisations focused on "countering organised border crime" (n=20), "countering irregular border crossing" (n=16), "raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration" (n=13) and "raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries" (n=13). A more detailed breakdown can be seen in Table 6.

		EU Countries	Non-EU Countries
Raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration	No	540	35
	Yes	167	13
Raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries	No	454	35
	Yes	253	13
Countering misinformation among migrants	No	569	40
	Yes	138	8
Countering misinformation among migrants	No	436	43
	Yes	271	5
Protection of migrants' human rights	No	355	34
	Yes	352	14
Migrant integration in host countries	No	297	38
	Yes	410	10
Migrant reintegration in countries of origin	No	642	47
	Yes	65	1
Monitoring media representations of migrants	No	617	44
	Yes	90	4
Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants	No	569	41
	Yes	138	7
Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants	No	648	37
	Yes	59	11
Countering organised border crime	No	603	28
	Yes	104	20

Countering irregular border crossing	No	614	32
	Yes	93	16
Other	No	577	43
	Yes	130	5

Table 6. Issues related to migration on which practitioners' organisations worked, by EU and non-EU countries.

After providing information on the focus of their organisation, practitioners were asked to specify the activities their organisation made use of, selecting from a range of options. Practitioners' overall responses are displayed in Table 7, below.

D2. In your organisation's work across the issues you highlighted, which of the following activities does your organisation make use of?

	No	Yes
Face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities	224	531
Online engagement with migrant individuals or communities	567	188
Policy work	536	219
Media activities for the general public	566	189
Media activities for a specialist audience	636	119
Arts- and culture-based activities	601	154
Face-to-face engagement with other professionals	404	351
Online engagement with other professionals	497	258

Table 7. Activities used by practitioners' organisations

As Table 7 shows, practitioners frequently made use of “face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities” (n=531) and “face-to-face engagement with other professionals” (n=351). Activities least used by practitioners included “media activities for a specialist audience” (n=119) and “arts- and culture-based activities” (n=154).

Theme 2:

Practitioners' assessments of the potential success of activities to address misinformation amongst migrants

Research question:

How successful do first-line practitioners believe different types of activities can be in addressing misinformation among migrants?

Key findings:

- Practitioners considered face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities and face-to-face engagement with other professionals to be the two most promising activities in addressing misinformation amongst migrants.
- Non-EU practitioners, as well as practitioners working in countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants, tended to assess the two above-mentioned activities as slightly more promising than other groups of practitioners.
- Practitioners generally considered online engagement with migrant individuals or communities and arts- and culture-based activities to be the least promising activities.
- Non-EU practitioners, as well as practitioners working in countering organised border crime and in countering irregular border crossing, tended to assess the two above-mentioned activities as slightly less promising than other groups of practitioners.

In the section of the survey focused on best practices, practitioners were first asked, based on their own experience or their knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, to assess the potential success of different types of activities that could address misinformation among migrants (about conditions on migration routes, in host countries, etc.). These activities were:

- Face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities.
- Online engagement with migrant individuals or communities.
- Policy work.
- Media activities for the general public.
- Media activities for a specialist audience.
- Arts- and culture-based activities.
- Face-to-face engagement with other professionals.
- Online engagement with other professionals.

To make their assessments, practitioners ranked the diverse activities on a scale from 0-7, in which 0 indicated that the activity could not be successful at all in addressing misinformation among migrants (about conditions on migration routes, in host countries, etc.), and 7 indicated that the strategy could be very successful. Practitioners’ assessments of the activities are displayed in Table 8, below.

D3. Based on your own experience or your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how successful do you believe the following types of activity could be in addressing misinformation among migrants (about conditions on migration routes, in host countries, etc.)?

	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities	19	9	27	55	95	148	149	253
Online engagement with migrant individuals or communities	54	57	81	132	147	135	82	67
Policy work	27	35	62	107	152	136	128	108
Media activities for the general public	32	40	48	104	147	154	126	104
Media activities for a specialist audience	29	40	37	110	154	155	116	114
Arts- and culture-based activities	42	58	64	126	140	150	91	84

Face-to-face engagement with other professionals	13	28	27	87	136	171	144	149
Online engagement with other professionals	33	41	54	110	164	139	124	90

Table 8. Practitioners' assessments of the potential success of different activities in addressing misinformation among migrants

As can be seen in Table 8, first-line practitioners surveyed were inclined to consider “face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities” as the most promising tool to combat misinformation amongst migrants. Of the 755 responses received to this item, 645 (85.43%) were above 3, and 402 (53.25%) were above 5.

The second most potentially successful strategy, according to practitioners, was “face-to-face engagement with other professionals”. Of the 755 responses received to this question, 600 (79.47%) were above 3, and 293 (38.80%) were above 5. These results underline the importance of face-to-face relationships when working with both migrants and other professionals.

On the other hand, “online engagement with migrant individuals or communities” and “arts- and culture-based activities” were the

initiatives that were least positively assessed by participants. Indeed, of the 755 participants, 324 (42.91%) assigned a rating of 4 or below to online engagement, and 290 (38.95%) to culture-based activities. However, these two activities were assessed more positively by some first-line practitioners (37.62% rated “online engagement with migrant individuals or communities” above 4, and 44.05% rated “arts- and culture-based activities” above 4), suggesting that they may have some degree of relevance in addressing misinformation amongst migrants.

Despite these general trends, there were some notable differences between the assessments of practitioners based in EU countries and their counterparts in non-EU countries, as displayed in Table 9.

D3. Based on your own experience or your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how successful do you believe the following types of activity could be in addressing misinformation among migrants (about conditions on migration routes, in host countries, etc.)?

		mean	sd	IQR	0%	25%	50%	75%	100%
Face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities	EU	5.262	1.753	3	0	4	6	7	7
	Non-EU	6.104	1.134	2	3	5	7	7	7
Online engagement with migrant individuals or communities	EU	3.816	1.929	2	0	3	4	5	7
	Non-EU	2.938	2.025	3	0	1	3	4	7
Policy work	EU	4.376	1.847	3	0	3	4	6	7
	Non-EU	4.125	2.130	4	0	2	4	6	7
Media activities for the general public	EU	4.322	1.870	3	0	3	5	6	7
	Non-EU	4.875	1.975	3	0	4	5	7	7
Media activities for a specialist audience	EU	4.373	1.844	3	0	3	5	6	7
	Non-EU	4.938	1.983	3	0	4	5	7	7
Arts- and culture-based activities	EU	3.952	1.920	2	0	3	4	5	7
	Non-EU	4.458	2.221	4	0	3	5	7	7
Face-to-face engagement with other professionals	EU	4.799	1.705	2	0	4	5	6	7
	Non-EU	5.333	1.814	3	1	4	5.5	7	7
Online engagement with other professionals	EU	4.321	1.825	3	0	3	4	6	7
	Non-EU	3.104	2.086	2.25	0	1.75	3	4	7

Table 9. EU and non-EU practitioners' assessments of the potential success of different activities in addressing misinformation among migrants

As Table 9 demonstrates, whilst both practitioners from EU and non-EU countries considered “face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities” and “face-to-face engagement with other professionals” to be the two most potentially successful activities, practitioners from non-EU countries tended to assess these activities as slightly more successful than their EU counterparts. The means of the non-EU practitioners’ assessment of the two activities were 6.104 (SD= 1.134) and 5.333 (SD=1.814), respectively, whilst the means of their EU counterparts’ assessments were 5.262 (SD=1.753) and 4.799 (SD=1.705), respectively.

In addition, practitioners working in non-EU countries tended to consider “online engagement with migrant individuals or communities” and “online engagement with other professionals” as less successful than practitioners based in EU countries. The mean for these items in EU countries were 3.816 (SD=1.929) and 4.321 (SD=1.825), respectively, whilst in non-EU countries the means were 2.938 (SD=2.025) and 3.104 (SD=2.086), respectively.

Practitioners working in different areas also made slightly different assessments of the potential success of the activities listed.

For example, in general, all groups of practitioners considered “face-to-face work with migrants” to be potentially successful in addressing misinformation. However, practitioners working in the field of “countering extremism, radicalisation, and

violence against migrants” assessed such face-to-face work especially positively, with a mean score of 5.8, compared to their counterparts working in other areas. In a similar vein, certain types of practitioners considered “face-to-face work with other professionals” to be especially successful. These were practitioners working on “countering misinformation amongst migrants” (5.247) (SD=1.488), “countering extremism, radicalisation and violence against migrants” (5.151) (SD=1.515), and “countering extremism, radicalisation and violence by migrants” (5.142) (SD=1.687).

In terms of activities assessed as relatively less successful in general, “online engagement with migrants” was assessed particularly negatively by practitioners working in “countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants” (3.857) (SD= 1.913), “countering organised border crime” (3.604) (SD=2.019), and “countering irregular border crossing” (3.357) (SD=2.07). Similarly, practitioners working in “countering organised border crime” and “countering irregular border crossing” considered “arts- and culture-based activities” to be less successful than their counterparts working in other areas ((3.733) (SD=1.1896) and (3.275) (SD=1.784), respectively). However, it is worth noting that practitioners working in “countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants” (4.662) (SD=1.65) and “countering misinformation among migrants” (4.616) (SD=1.67) assessed arts- and culture-based activities as somewhat more successful than other groups.

Theme 3:

Practitioners' assessment of criteria through which to evaluate the success of activities in migration-related work

Research question:

What criteria do first-line practitioners believe should be used when evaluating the success of activities in migration-related work?

Key findings:

- Regardless of their fields of work, as well as whether they were from EU or non-EU countries, practitioners assessed protection of human rights as the most important criterion for evaluating the success of activities in migration-related work.
- Similarly, across fields and location, practitioners assessed the transferability of an activity or practice as the least important criterion for evaluating its success.
- A plurality of practitioners identified involvement of the beneficiaries of an activity and the beneficiaries' satisfaction with an activity as additional criteria through which to evaluate the activity's success.

Practitioners' ranking of the importance of five set criteria in evaluating the success of activities

As well as evaluating the potential success of specific practices in combating misinformation amongst migrants, practitioners were also asked to evaluate the importance of criteria through which to measure the success of practices in their work in general. They were asked, based on their experience or knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, to rank the importance of the following criteria, adapted from the work of Spathi et al. (2021):

- Overall impact,
- Protection of human rights,
- Sustainability,
- Transferability,
- Intersectoral coordination.

To make this assessment, practitioners ranked the diverse criteria on a scale from 1-5, in which 1 indicated that the criteria was the most important factor, and 5 was the least important. Figure 8 shows practitioners' overall rankings.

Figure 8. Practitioners' ranking of criteria through which to assess the success of activities in migration-related work.

The most highly ranked criterion was “protection of human rights”, with 400 participants (52.98%) ranking it in first place, and 126 participants ranking it in second place (16.69%). This is in line with consortium partners’ evaluation of the same criteria, who also selected “protection of human rights” as most the important criterion (Spathi et al., 2021, p. 26).

Also in line with consortium partners’ evaluations (Spathi et al. 2021, p. 26), practitioners ranked the criterion “transferability” as least important. Of the 755 responses to this question, only 28 (3.71%) ranked this criterion in first place, and only 83 (10.99%) ranked it in second place.

The tendency to rank “protection of human rights” in first place, and “transferability” in last place was shared by both EU and non-EU practitioners (see Table 10).

		1	2	3	4	5	Total
Overall impact	EU	17.26	21.07	18.53	16.83	26.31	100
	Non-EU	20.83	20.83	12.50	12.50	33.33	100
Protection of human rights	EU	52.9	16.69	12.59	10.89	6.93	100
	Non-EU	54.17	16.67	18.75	6.25	4.17	100
Sustainability	EU	15.98	24.19	26.45	21.92	11.46	100
	Non-EU	8.33	22.92	29.17	29.17	10.42	100
Transferability	EU	3.82	11.32	19.94	27.44	37.48	100
	Non-EU	2.08	6.25	22.92	33.33	35.42	100
Intersectoral coordination	EU	10.04	26.73	22.49	22.91	17.82	100
	Non-EU	14.58	33.33	16.67	18.75	16.67	100

Table 10. Practitioners' ranking of criteria through which to assess best practices, by percentage of EU or non-EU practitioners

In general, practitioners working on all types of issues related to migration also tended to rank “protection of human rights” in first place and “transferability” in last place (see Annex 2). However, practitioners working on migrant integration in host countries, protection of human rights, and countering discrimination against migrants tended to rank “protection of human rights” very highly (223, 213, and 156 practitioners from each group, respectively, ranked protection of human rights as the most important criterion). Many of these practitioners also ranked “transferability” in last place (163, 143, 112 practitioners per group, respectively).

In addition to selecting from the five criteria offered, practitioners were also prompted to list any other criteria they considered important when assessing the success of activities and practices in migration-related work. A total of 118 practitioners responded to this prompt, all of whom were practitioners based in EU countries.

In the responses, some participants developed and nuanced the criteria already mentioned. For example, in terms of economic sustainability, some participants referred to the cost of an activity, the cost-benefit ratio, and evaluation of processes and accountability as important

criteria to assess success. Others developed ideas based on intersectoral coordination, commenting that the degree of networking between associations and entities working in the same field, coordination between governmental departments, and overall intersectoral approach and representation were key criteria. In a similar vein, some participants made reference to the defence of human rights as a key criterion through which to assess success, mentioning civil and social rights, as well as equality and a humanistic approach to work, as particularly important factors.

Other participants, however, mentioned factors not encompassed by the original five criteria. Many of these responses highlighted the role of the beneficiaries of a particular activity or practice in evaluating its success. Two main evaluation criteria were apparent in the responses.

- 1) Involvement of beneficiaries in the proposed activities and their evaluation. Examples of responses of this nature include:

“Direct involvement of the target groups”; “Inclusion of migrants and refugees”; “Commitment of all stakeholders involved/ Participatory design”; “Direct contact with and involvement of the target groups”; “Target groups are reached”; “Target group involvement”; “Whether migrant people play an active role, in both the design and the implementation and evaluation of the results”; “Participation of the target population in the design of the programs”; “Migrants should play an active role”; “Including migrants themselves in leadership roles and in delivering activities”

- 2) Beneficiaries’ satisfaction with or gain from the proposed activity. Examples of responses include:

“Accommodation to a suitable social service”; “To use psychological help”; “Well-being”; “Mental wellbeing”; “Social integration of migrants”; “Accompaniment and integration of migrants on the territory”; “Satisfaction of the beneficiaries with the activities”; “The situation of the immigrants and their mental health”; “Impact on migrant groups (taking into account their needs and suggestions)”; “Migrant satisfaction around access to quality employment”, “access to higher education, access to healthcare); “Relevance for people seeking asylum”; “The needs of the target group”.

Other, more general, criteria that participants mentioned included:

“Transnational political processes”; “Municipalism”; “Gender impact”; “Constant evaluation and improvement”; “Awareness-raising in countries of origin, and for rich countries to pay their debts to developing countries”; and “(Preventative) supranational policies to promote development in countries of origin”, among others.

Theme 4: Practitioners' use and assessment of ICT tools in migration-related work

Research question:

- How do first-line practitioners currently use ICT tools in their work on migration?
- How do first-line practitioners assess current ICT tools in their fields of work?

Key findings:

- First-line practitioners used ICT tools for a range of purposes in their work, especially for education and training and accessing data on migration.
- It was less common for practitioners to use ICT tools for the purposes of enabling peer-to-peer connections between migrants and/or for enabling connections between migrants and stakeholders.
- Existing ICT solutions were generally considered effective, user-friendly, and understandable.
- ICT solutions used to share guidelines with other practitioners/stakeholders and to share information with migrants were considered particularly effective, user-friendly, and understandable.
- Practitioners working in raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration and in monitoring media representations of migrants considered existing solutions to be particularly satisfactory.

ICT solutions used by practitioners working on different migration-related issues

To explore practitioners' current engagement with ICT tools, survey participants were asked to select the purpose for which they most frequently used such tools in their work.

As can be seen in Figure 9, below, practitioners tended to use ICT tools for “accessing data on migration”, “migrant education and training” and “practitioner/stakeholder education and training”. In contrast, it was less common for practitioners to use ICT tools for “enabling peer-to-peer connections between migrants” and “enabling connections between migrants and practitioners/stakeholders”.

ICT2. You mentioned that your organisation uses ICT tools for the following purposes. For which purpose does your organisation most often use ICT tools?

Figure 9. Use of ICT tools by practitioners' organisations

As Table 11 shows, practitioners who worked on different issues made use of different types of ICT tools. For example, practitioners working on the majority of issues described in the survey³ most frequently used ICT tools for “accessing data on migration” and “practitioner/stakeholder education and training”. However, practitioners working on “countering discrimination against migrants” and “countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants” also frequently used ICT tools for “migrant education and training”.

³ These were practitioners who worked on the following issues: “raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration”, “raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries”, “countering misinformation amongst migrants”, “protection of migrants' human rights”, “migrant integration in host countries”, “migrant reintegration in countries of origin”, “monitoring media representations of migrants”, “countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants”, “countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants”, “countering organised border crime”, and “countering irregular border crossing”

Key D1 ICT tools:

1= Accessing data on migration

2= Enabling connections between migrants and practitioners/stakeholders

3= Enabling peer-to-peer connections between migrants

4= Migrant education and training

5= Monitoring media or social media

6 = Practitioner and stakeholder education and training

7= Sharing guidelines and practices with other practitioners/stakeholders

8= Sharing information with migrants

9 = Sharing migrants' own stories and opinions

D1 ICT tools		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Total organisations		66	16	8	67	27	89	32	44	25
Raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration	No	41	11	7	45	15	66	17	31	18
	Yes	25	5	1	22	12	23	15	13	7
Raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries	No	30	8	4	35	14	45	14	23	16
	Yes	36	8	4	32	13	44	18	21	9
Countering misinformation among migrants	No	46	10	6	51	14	68	22	27	16
	Yes	20	6	2	16	13	21	10	17	9
Countering discrimination against migrants	No	27	3	3	26	13	40	12	17	9
	Yes	39	13	5	41	14	49	20	27	16
Protection of migrants' human rights	No	18	6	5	26	12	30	9	18	11
	Yes	48	10	3	41	15	59	23	26	14
Migrant integration in host countries	No	17	1	2	8	12	26	11	8	7
	Yes	49	15	6	59	15	63	21	36	18
Migrant reintegration in countries of origin	No	49	13	7	63	25	79	29	40	24
	Yes	17	3	1	4	2	10	3	4	1

D1 ICT tools		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Monitoring media representations of migrants	No	51	12	6	54	15	72	19	36	16
	Yes	15	4	2	13	12	17	13	8	9
Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants	No	47	8	5	46	15	56	20	32	15
	Yes	19	8	3	21	12	33	12	12	10
Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants	No	57	14	5	62	25	72	27	38	21
	Yes	9	2	3	5	2	17	5	6	4
Countering organised border crime	No	48	13	7	58	24	75	25	36	19
	Yes	18	3	1	9	3	14	7	8	6
Countering irregular border crossing	No	46	16	5	65	24	83	29	41	22
	Yes	20	0	3	2	3	6	3	3	3
Other	No	54	16	8	53	21	75	28	39	23
	Yes	12	0	0	14	6	14	4	5	2

Table 11. Use of ICT tools by issue on which practitioners worked.

The effectiveness, understandability and user-friendliness of ICT solutions

To gauge their satisfaction with existing ICT tools in migration-related work, first-line practitioners were asked about the degree to which they found such tools to be effective, user-friendly, and understandable⁴. The scale used to evaluate the tools ranged from 0, meaning “not effective/user-friendly/understandable at all” to 7, meaning “very effective/user-friendly/understandable”. Participants were asked to consider effectiveness, user-friendliness, and understandability in relation to the most common purposes for which their organisation used ICT tools, which included the following purposes:

- Accessing data on migration
- Enabling connections between migrants and practitioners/stakeholders
- Enabling peer-to-peer connections between migrants
- Migrant education and training
- Monitoring media or social media
- Practitioner/stakeholder education and training
- Sharing guidelines and practices with other practitioners/stakeholders
- Sharing information with migrants
- Sharing migrants’ own stories and opinions

First, practitioners were asked about how effective they found existing ICT tools for particular purposes. It is worth noting that, for all purposes for which ICT tools were used, existing solutions obtained values above 4.5, on average. However, “sharing guidelines and practices with other practitioners/stakeholders” and “sharing information with migrants” were considered to be the categories in which existing solutions were most effective.

Compared to other groups of practitioners, those working in “raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration” (4.967) (SD=1.384), “monitoring media representations of migrants” (4.978)

(SD=1.206) and “countering organised border crime” (4.898) (SD=1.341) considered existing ICT solutions to be particularly effective.

Practitioners were also asked about how user-friendly they considered existing ICT solutions to be. Overall, participants assessed existing ICT tools for the purposes of “sharing guidelines and practices with other practitioners/stakeholders” (mean 5.063, SD=1.544) and “sharing information with migrants” (mean 5.023, SD=1.338) as the most user-friendly. Although none of the categories of use for ICT tools obtained an average score of less than 4, “enabling peer-to-peer connections between migrants” was assessed

⁴ It should be noted that the ICT section of the survey only appeared for participants who had previously stated that their organisation used some type of ICT-based practice. The filter criteria were having selected one or more of the following options in D1: online engagement with migrants; online engagement with professionals; media activities for the general public; arts- and culture-based activities.

as the category in which solutions were least user-friendly.

Existing ICT solutions were considered particularly user-friendly by practitioners working in “raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration” (4.878) (SD=1.364), “monitoring media representations of migrants” (4.817) (SD=1.284) and “raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries” (4.898) (SD=1.341), compared to practitioners working in other fields.

Finally, practitioners were asked about the understandability of existing ICT solutions for particular purposes. Existing solutions for the purposes of “sharing guidelines and practices

with other practitioners/stakeholders” (mean 5.156, SD=1.483), “practitioner/stakeholder education and training” (mean 5.022, SD=1.252), and “sharing information with migrants” (mean 5.0) were considered most understandable.

Practitioners engaged in “raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration” (4.918) (SD=1.417), “monitoring media representations of migrants” (4.946) (SD=1.219) and “raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries” (4.8) (SD=1.326) considered existing solutions to be particularly understandable.

Section 4:

Conclusions & Discussions

This report has presented the results of a survey with 755 first-line practitioners, a group identified as an under-studied population in migration research (Bayerl et al., 2020).

The survey was carried out in the spring of 2022, a time frame which is significant for several reasons. Firstly, the majority of respondents indicated that, during this time, their organisations were still being impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. 65.87% of practitioners considered that their organisations were being moderately to severely affected by the pandemic. Whilst this does suggest the burden of the pandemic has lessened since the first iteration of the survey, in which 67.3% percent of practitioners indicated their organisations had been severely affected by the pandemic, it highlights the continued impact of the pandemic on migration-related work. In addition to the pandemic, many anecdotal reports indicated that the war in Ukraine had a significant impact on practitioners and their organisations at the time of the survey, with the crisis hindering recruitment in some countries.

Results reflect the views of practitioners from a range of countries across and beyond the EU, but it should be noted that female FLPs working in support services in European countries are the most represented groups in the sample.

The predominance of practitioners working in support services may have influenced the issues on which the sample most commonly worked. Although, overall, practitioners worked on a range of different issues related to migration, protection of human rights was the most frequent focus. However, there were some differences between practitioners in European and non-European countries. Whilst EU participants most frequently focused on migrant integration in host countries and protection of migrants' human rights in their work, their non-EU counterparts were most frequently engaged in countering organised border crime and irregular border crossing, and raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration and about laws and conditions in host countries.

Practitioners in the sample also used a range of activities in their work, but most frequently relied on activities based on face-to-face contact (both with migrants, communities, and other professionals). As well as being the most used activities, face-to-face activities were also those considered to be the most potentially successful in addressing misinformation amongst migrants. The value given to face-to-face activities was the same for both EU and non-EU participants, and for participants working on a range of different

issues related to migration. Practitioners' emphasis on face-to-face contact when working with misinformation amongst migrants is a notable finding from this survey, as strategies to address misinformation have been identified as a particularly important line of research by the PERCEPTIONS project (Bayerl et al., 2020, pp. 31). Furthermore, it is in line with feedback from first-line practitioners in other tasks in the project – which has also placed emphasis on in-person contact with migrants (Deppieri & Mana, 2022) – as well as with literature which highlights the importance of face-to-face relationships for migrant groups (Parella, 2007).

The circumstances in which the survey took place should, nevertheless, also be taken into account to contextualise the importance placed on face-to-face work. In a pandemic described as a “pandemic of social isolation” (Holt-Lunstad, 2021), it is possible that in-person contact may have taken on an increased importance for participants, compared to the pre-COVID-19 period. Some studies are beginning to show, for example, how individuals are re-valuing face-to-face interactions after living through various types of lock-down scenarios in which social contact was severely restricted (Ekwonye & Truong, 2021; Tomaino et al., 2021).

Activities that practitioners considered least successful in addressing misinformation amongst migrants were online engagement with migrant individuals or communities and arts- and culture-based activities. This finding is of note as it contrasts with other work in the PERCEPTIONS project, in which practitioners considered arts- and culture-based activities as potentially useful in addressing misinformation, engaging communities, and building trust and shared values (Deppieri & Mana, 2022). As such, it would be worth exploring the value of such activities in more depth in further research. Literature does suggest, for example, that art can be a channel of communication able to promote social sensitivity (Mesías Lema, 2018). This could be particularly important for the intercultural and interpersonal dimensions of work with

migrants (García-Carmona et al., 2021b), especially as the academic training of first-line practitioners currently places little emphasis on artistic approaches (López Fernández, 2020).

In addition, although practitioners considered face-to-face work promising and arts- and culture-based activities as less so, it is worth noting that such assessments may be in part dependent upon the profiles of the practitioners surveyed. That is to say, practitioners already using a particular activity in their work could be inclined to consider such activities as more promising than those who do not. In this sample, a plurality of practitioners used face-to-face work (70% of practitioners used face-to-face activities with migrants, and 46% used face-to-face activities with other professionals), whilst only 17% used arts- and culture-based activities.

In terms of evaluating the success of best practices in migration-related work, practitioners ranked the importance of five potential criteria through which to assess the success of a practice: overall impact, protection of human rights, intersectorial coordination, sustainability, and transferability. Overall, and regardless of the issue on which they worked, practitioners generally considered the degree of protection of human rights to be the most important criterion for evaluation. In contrast, the transferability of a practice was assessed as the least important evaluation criterion. Practitioners' ranking of the most and least important evaluation criteria is in line with consortium partners' own rankings (Spathi et al., 2021) of the same criteria. In addition, a select group of practitioners highlighted beneficiaries' involvement, satisfaction, and gain from a practice as additional criteria through which to evaluate a practice's success. Overall, practitioners' views echo results from other projects related to best practices in migration-related work, which have emphasised criteria like inherent participation and engagement (European Website on Integration, 2021; Mateus & Pinho, 2018; Protection Working

Cluster Group, n.d.), respect for human rights (Mateus & Pinho, 2018; Protection Working Cluster Group, n.d.), and migrant integration (Juzwiak et al., 2014) as key points of reference for selecting best practices.

Practitioners used a range of ICT tools in their work, especially for education and training (for practitioners, stakeholders, and migrants alike), and for accessing data on migration. In general practitioners considered existing ICT solutions to be effective, user-friendly, and understandable. Practitioners working on raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration and monitoring media representations of migrants, as well as practitioners who used ICT tools to share guidelines with other practitioners/stakeholders and to share information with migrants, tended to evaluate existing solutions as especially positive. This is in line with some literature that positions ICTs as useful tools for building environments in which individuals and communities can learn and take action to promote social justice, intercultural education, and social inclusion (Vrasidas et al., 2009; Willems, 2019).

In conclusion, in combination with the results from the first iteration of the survey (García-Carmona et al., 2021a), these results add to the picture of how first-line practitioners view their own work. In general, the first-line practitioners surveyed in the PERCEPTIONS project seem satisfied with their work, and see various activities they use, particularly those based on face-to-face contact, as successful in addressing misinformation amongst migrants. They are similarly satisfied with the ICT tools they most frequently use. However, it should be noted that, in the first iteration of the survey, first-line practitioners did identify several barriers to their work (legal constraints, insufficient human resources, stress or psychological burden caused by the work performed, insufficient salary, and lack of necessary facilities or infrastructure), which should be taken into consideration. The results also shed light on practitioners' professional values, showing that practitioners across the spectrum consider the protection of human rights to be a key criterion through which to assess the success of their work.

Limitations and future research

As mentioned, the views presented in this report are largely representative of female practitioners working in support organisations in EU countries. As it is not known to what extent this profile is representative of the population of first-line practitioners overall, these results should be taken as exploratory.

The results presented here are almost purely quantitative, which has its limitations when exploring the complex phenomenon of migration-related work. However, such quantitative work is important, in this case as it has helped to identify general attitudes toward the scope of “good practices” and general criteria through which to evaluate the success of “good practices” in the field of migration. These results can serve to inform future research, which should ideally combine other methodological approaches and tools (for example, qualitative research like semi-structured interviews, ethnography, etc.) in order to deepen knowledge of best practices and use of ICT tools, both from the perspectives of first-line practitioners and migrants.

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Annex 1: Survey questionnaire

Start of Block: Introduction and informed consent

You are invited to participate in a survey about **best practices in migration-related work**. By best practices, we mean activities that successfully address challenges related to migration (e.g., human trafficking, discrimination, misinformation, etc.).

The survey is part of **PERCEPTIONS (Grant Agreement number: 833870)**, a Horizon 2020 project which explores how Europe and the EU are seen by current and potential migrants.

The information gathered through this survey will help the project to create tools to support both migrants and professionals working in the field of migration.

The main survey will take around **8 minutes** to answer. There is also an optional section on professional wellbeing and intercultural attitudes, which would take another 2 minutes.

Your participation in this study is **completely voluntary**, and you have the right to withdraw from the survey without any repercussions at any time.

Types of questions asked: This survey contains questions on challenges related to migration and best practices in migration-related work, and an optional section on work psychology. We will also ask some basic questions about you (e.g. age, gender identity, etc.). You will not be asked to provide any name or contact details, and no IP addresses will be stored or tracked.

Privacy and data security: No personally identifiable information is collected. There is no way to trace your responses back to you or your organisation. All data will be aggregated prior to analysis.

Data collection purpose: The data will be analysed by partners in the PERCEPTIONS project. The aggregated and anonymised results of this survey will be included in scientific research databases, reports, presentations and conferences, and briefs for practitioners and policymakers.

Data retention: The anonymised and aggregated data will be securely stored and retained for a period of 24 months after the end of the project, namely until 2025 at the latest.

Data controller: Universidad de Granada

Contact points: If you have any questions about the research study, or want to receive a summary of the main findings, please send an email to: benenwhitworth@ugr.es

Thank you in advance for your participation!

Informed consent

By checking the box below, you confirm that you:

- Consent to participating in the survey
- Consent to the processing of the data from your responses for the purposes mentioned previously
- Are at least 18 years old

I consent

A. Professional information

A1. What type of organisation do you work for?

Please check the option that best applies.

Governmental (public organisations working in one country) (1)

Intergovernmental (public organisations working across more than one country
e.g. EU organisations) (2)

Non-governmental (faith-based) (3)

Non-governmental (non-faith based) (4)

Private company (5)

Freelancer (6)

Other (please specify in the next question) (7)

If What type of organisation do you work for? = Other (please specify in the next question)

A1 Please specify the type of organisation you work for.

A2. In what country do you work?

(Afghanistan (1) ... Zimbabwe (1357))

A3. What city do you work in?

A4. On what level does your organisation mostly work?

International (1)

Federal/national (2)

State/prefectural (3)

Local/communal (4)

A5. In what sector does your organisation **primarily** operate?

(Only one option can be selected)

- Border enforcement (1)
- Child services (2)
- Customs enforcement (3)
- Immigrant advocacy (9)
- Internal law enforcement (12)
- Immigrant integration (11)
- Diplomatic (consulates, etc.) (5)
- Labour services (14)
- Governance and policymaking (6)
- Psychological services (counselling, pastoral support, etc.) (16)
- Judiciary (13)
- Social welfare services (17)
- Legal services (legal aid, etc.) (15)
- Women's services (women's shelters, domestic violence counselling, etc.) (18)
- Immigration and asylum services (10)
- Youth work (19)
- Education or VET (4)
- Other (20)
- Health services (7)
- Housing services (8)

If In what sector does your organisation primarily operate? = Other

A5 Please specify the sector in which your organisation works.

B. COVID-19 and migration-related work

B1. Thinking of the period between December 2020 and now, how severely has the pandemic affected your organisation's operations?

	1- not at all (1)	2 (4)	3 (5)	4 (6)	5 (7)	6 (8)	7- very severely (9)	Don't know (10)
(5)								

C. Practitioner contact with migrants

C1. How often do you have contact with recently-arrived migrants from non-EU countries during the course of your work? Please consider your organisation's target groups here, **not** your co-workers.

	Never (1)	Less than once a month (2)	Once a month (3)	Several times a month (4)	Once a week (5)	Several times a week (6)	Everyday (7)	Don't know (9)
(1)								

D. Best practices

D1. Does your organisation work on any of the following issues related to migration?

(Please check all that apply)

Raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration (1)

Raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries (2)

Countering misinformation among migrants (about conditions on migration routes, in host countries, etc.) (3)

Countering discrimination against migrants (4)

Protection of migrants' human rights (5)

Migrant integration in host countries (6)

Migrant reintegration in countries of origin (7)

Monitoring media representations of migrants (8)

Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants (9)

Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants (10)

Countering organised border crime (e.g., human trafficking, migrant smuggling, etc.) (11)

Countering irregular border crossing (12)

Other (19)

If Does your organisation work on any of the following issues related to migration? = Other

D1 Please specify the other issue related to migration on which your organisation works.

D2. In your organisation's work across the issues you highlighted, which of the following activities does your organisation make use of?

(Please check all that apply)

Face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities (counselling, neighbourhood workshops, peer-to-peer activities, etc.) (1)

Online engagement with migrant individuals or communities (counselling, social media campaigns, mobile apps, etc.) (2)

Policy work (drafting laws and regulations, policy guidelines, codes of conduct, etc.) (3)

Media activities for the general public (print media, online, TV, radio, etc.) (4)

Media activities for a specialist audience (white papers, guidelines, expert podcasts, etc.) (5)

Arts and culture-based activities (exhibitions, performances, festivals, etc.) (6)

Face-to-face engagement with other professionals (seminars, trainings, etc.) (7)

Online engagement with other professionals (webinars, e-learning/training, etc.) (8)

D3. Based on your own experience or your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how successful do you believe the following types of activity could be in addressing **misinformation among migrants (about conditions on migration routes, in host countries, etc.)?**

	0- not successful at all (2)	1 (3)	2 (4)	3 (6)	4 (7)	5 (8)	6 (9)	7- very successful (10)
Face-to-face engagement with migrant individuals or communities (1)								
Online engagement with migrant individuals or communities (2)								
Policy work (3)								
Media activities for the general public (4)								
Media activities for a specialist audience (5)								
Arts- and culture-based activities (6)								
Face-to-face engagement with other professionals (7)								
Online engagement with other professionals (8)								

D4. When assessing the success of activities like those we have mentioned, various criteria can be used. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?

(Please enter your scores (1-5) below to create your ranking, in which 1 is the most important factor, and 5 is the least important)

Overall impact (1)

Protection of human rights (e.g., of migrants and other target groups) (2)

Sustainability (i.e., can the activity be maintained/implemented over time?) (3)

Transferability (i.e., can the activity be transferred to other sites and contexts?) (4)

Intersectoral coordination (i.e., does the activity effectively involve multiple groups of stakeholders?) (5)

D5. When assessing the success of activities like those we have mentioned, are there other criteria you believe are highly important?

Yes (4)

No (5)

If When assessing the success of activities like those we have mentioned, are there other criteria y... = Yes

D5 Please specify the other criteria. (You may enter up to three).

ICT solutions

The next survey section deals with information and communications technology (ICT) tools. ICT tools include desktop, mobile, and online applications such as e-learning platforms, data sharing platforms, etc.

In this section, please consider specialised ICT tools for professionals who work on migration-related issues, not general-purpose apps like MS Office and Google. Examples are given in the first question below.

ICT1. Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its work on migration?

(Please check all that apply)

Practitioner/stakeholder education and training (example: <http://gvets.eu/resources/>) (1)

Migrant education and training (example: <https://moocs4inclusion.org/>) (2)

Sharing guidelines and practices with other practitioners/stakeholders
(example: <http://buildingtrust.eu/>) (3)

Sharing information with migrants (example: <https://rumoursaboutgermany.info/>) (4)

Sharing migrants' own stories and opinions (example: <https://www.awaremigrants.org/>) (5)

Enabling peer-to-peer connections between migrants
(example: <https://www.migrantsasmessengers.org/>) (6)

Enabling connections between migrants and practitioners/stakeholders
(example: <https://www.lawcentres.org.uk/>) (8)

Accessing data on migration (example: <https://www.traffikanalysis.org/>) (10)

Monitoring media or social media (example: <https://rumorfree.org/>) (11)

ICT2. You mentioned that your organisation uses ICT tools for the following purposes. For which purpose does your organisation **most often** use ICT tools?

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Practitioner/stakeholder education and training (example: <http://gvets.eu/resources/>)

Practitioner/stakeholder education and training (1)

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Migrant education and training (example: <https://moocs4inclusion.org/>)

Migrant education and training (2)

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Sharing guidelines and practices with other practitioners/stakeholders (example: <http://buildingtrust.eu/>)

Sharing guidelines and practices with other practitioners/stakeholders (3)

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Sharing information with migrants (example: <https://rumoursaboutgermany.info/>)

Sharing information with migrants (4)

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Sharing migrants' own stories and opinions (example: <https://www.awaremigrants.org/>)

Sharing migrants' own stories and opinions (5)

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Enabling peer-to-peer connections between migrants (example: <https://www.migrantsasmessengers.org/>)

Enabling peer-to-peer connections between migrants (6)

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Enabling connections between migrants and practitioners/stakeholders (example: <https://www.lawcentres.org.uk/>)

Enabling connections between migrants and practitioners/stakeholders (9)

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Accessing data on migration (example: <https://www.traffikanalysis.org/>)

Accessing data on migration (10)

If Does your organisation utilise ICT tools for any of the following purposes in the course of its w... = Monitoring media or social media (example: <https://rumorfree.org/>)

Monitoring media or social media (11)

ICT2. You mentioned that your organisation uses ICT tools for $\{ICT2/ChoiceGroup/SelectedChoices\}$. In general, how **effective**, **user-friendly**, and **easy to understand** do you find existing solutions in this category?

	0- not at all (1)	1 (2)	2 (3)	3 (4)	4 (5)	5 (6)	6 (7)	7- very (8)
Effective (overall, how well does the tool serve its intended purpose?) (1)								
User-friendly (how easy is the interface to use?) (2)								
Understandable (how easy is the content to understand?) (3)								

Background questions

Before we end, we would like to ask you some questions about your background. All data collected will remain fully anonymous.

J1. About how many years have you been working in your current field?

3 years or less (1)

4-8 years (2)

9-15 years (3)

More than 15 years (4)

J2. What is your gender identity?

Male (1)

Female (2)

Other (3)

Choose not to answer (4)

J3. How old are you?

18-19 (1)

20-29 (2)

30-39 (3)

40-49 (4)

50-59 (5)

60-69 (6)

70 or above (7)

Choose not to answer (8)

J4. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

Primary education (1)

Secondary education (2)

Vocational training or professional
certificate (3)

Bachelor's degree (4)

Master's degree (5)

Doctorate (6)

Response submission

You've now reached the end of the survey.

You may now submit your responses below, or choose to fill out an additional section on professional wellbeing and intercultural competences. The section is aimed at practitioners who work directly with migrants, and would take around 2 minutes to complete.

Please click below to select your choice.

I would like to fill out the additional section (1)

I would like to submit my responses now (2)

If You've now reached the end of the survey. You may now submit your responses below, or choose t... = I would like to fill out the additional section

Additional section

Thank you for choosing to fill out this section on professional wellbeing and intercultural competencies.

The questions included aim to shed the light on the importance of intercultural skills and personal well-being in the course of everyday work with migrants.

Please remember that no personally identifiable information is collected in this survey. There is no way to trace your responses back to you or your organisation, and all data will be aggregated prior to analysis.

W1. Reflecting on your work experience with migrants, please rate how frequently you experience the following statements.

	0 - Never (1)	1 - A few times a year (2)	2 - Once a month (3)	3 - A few times a month (4)	4 - Once a week (5)	5 - A few times a week (6)	6 - Every day (7)	7 - very (8)
I deal very effectively with the problems of migrants (1)								
I feel I'm positively influencing other people's lives through my work (6)								
I feel exhilarated after working closely with migrants (9)								

I feel I treat some migrants as if they were impersonal objects (2)								
I feel emotionally drained from my work (3)								
I feel fatigued when I get up in the morning and have to face another day on the job (4)								
I've become more callous towards people since I took this job (5)								
Working with people all day is really a strain for me (7)								
I don't really care what happens to some migrants (8)								

W2. Read each statement and select the response that best describes your capabilities. Please select the answer that best describes you as you really are.

	1 - Strongly disagree (1)	2 - Disagree (2)	3 - Somewhat disagree (3)	4 - Neither agree nor disagree (4)	5 - Somewhat agree (5)	6 - Agree (7)	7 - Strongly agree (8)
I know the cultural values and religious beliefs of other cultures (3)							
I know the rules (e.g., vocabulary, grammar) of other languages (2)							
I enjoy interacting with people from different cultures (1)							
I change my verbal behavior (e.g., accent, tone) when a cross-cultural interaction requires it (4)							

I use pause and silence differently to suit different cross-cultural situations (16)							
I am confident that I can socialize with locals in a culture that is unfamiliar to me (5)							
I know the arts and crafts of other cultures (6)							

W3. Read each statement and select the response that best describes your capabilities. Please select the answer that best describes you, as you really are.

	1 - Strongly disagree (1)	2 - Disagree (2)	3 - Somewhat disagree (3)	4 - Neither agree nor disagree (4)	5 - Somewhat agree (5)	6 - Agree (7)	7 - Strongly agree (8)
I know the legal and economic systems of other cultures (8)							
I know the rules for expressing nonverbal behaviors in other cultures (9)							
I change my nonverbal behavior when a cross-cultural situation requires it (10)							
I alter my facial expressions when a cross-cultural interaction requires it (11)							
I am sure I can deal with the stresses of adjusting to a culture that is new to me (12)							

I enjoy living in cultures that are unfamiliar to me (13)							
I vary the rate of my speaking when a cross-cultural situation requires it (15)							

W4. What type of training focusing on how to deal with people from different cultures have you attended in your professional life?

(Please check all that apply)

Cultural diversity training or intercultural training (1)

Gender diversity training (2)

LGBTQIA+ training (4)

Other (5)

I have never attended such a training (6)

If What type of training focusing on how to deal with people from different cultures have you attend... = Other

W4 Please specify what other type of training you attended.

W5. Thinking about your everyday practice, how frequently do you encounter a language barrier with migrants?

Never (i.e. once a year or less) (1)

Often (i.e. once a week) (5)

Rarely (i.e. once a month) (2)

Always (i.e. almost every day) (6)

Sometimes (i.e. once every two weeks) (4)

W6. How many languages do you speak in your daily work (with migrants)?

One (1)

Two (2)

Three (4)

Four or more (5)

Annex 2: Practitioners' ranking of evaluation criteria for best practices, by the issue on which their organisation worked.

(D1) Raising awareness about risks associated with irregular migration					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	35	37	30	27	51
Protection of human rights	99	30	25	15	11
Sustainability	22	46	53	38	21
Transferability	6	17	31	54	72
Intersectoral coordination	18	50	41	46	25

(D1) Raising awareness about laws and conditions in host countries					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	47	43	56	48	72
Protection of human rights	155	47	27	24	13
Sustainability	35	72	70	62	27
Transferability	8	30	49	72	107
Intersectoral coordination	21	74	64	60	47

(D1) Countering misinformation among migrants					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	28	28	27	22	41
Protection of human rights	83	25	19	14	5
Sustainability	22	39	37	37	11
Transferability	5	12	29	36	64
Intersectoral coordination	8	42	34	37	25

(D1) Countering discrimination against migrants					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	52	57	49	47	71
Protection of human rights	156	51	32	24	13
Sustainability	44	63	76	71	22
Transferability	6	29	57	72	112
Intersectoral coordination	18	76	62	62	58

(D1) Protection of migrants' human rights					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	57	78	74	60	97
Protection of human rights	213	66	43	25	19
Sustainability	49	79	104	87	47
Transferability	13	34	68	108	143
Intersectoral coordination	34	109	77	86	60

(D1) Migrant integration in host countries					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	69	83	88	71	109
Protection of human rights	223	75	52	47	23
Sustainability	71	102	98	100	49
Transferability	17	41	89	110	163
Intersectoral coordination	40	119	93	92	76

(D1) Migrant reintegration in countries of origin					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	11	13	5	16	21
Protection of human rights	40	11	5	4	6
Sustainability	9	24	13	12	8
Transferability	3	4	20	15	24
Intersectoral coordination	3	14	23	19	7

(D1) Monitoring media representations of migrants					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	17	22	13	13	29
Protection of human rights	50	18	15	9	2
Sustainability	17	20	24	19	14
Transferability	4	10	20	28	32
Intersectoral coordination	6	24	22	25	17

(D1) Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence against migrants					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	27	27	29	22	40
Protection of human rights	84	26	19	12	4
Sustainability	20	38	37	37	13
Transferability	2	13	28	41	61
Intersectoral coordination	12	41	32	33	27

(D1) Countering extremism, radicalisation, and violence by migrants					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	14	11	9	12	24
Protection of human rights	32	16	10	8	4
Sustainability	13	17	13	20	7
Transferability	2	7	20	17	24
Intersectoral coordination	9	19	18	13	11

(D1) Countering organised border crime					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	22	27	25	14	36
Protection of human rights	69	20	17	12	6
Sustainability	15	29	30	32	18
Transferability	3	13	24	34	50
Intersectoral coordination	15	35	28	32	14

(D1) Countering irregular border crossing					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	26	21	20	13	29
Protection of human rights	50	17	17	16	9
Sustainability	11	30	28	25	15
Transferability	6	12	20	30	41
Intersectoral coordination	16	29	24	25	15

(D1) Other					
D4. Based on your own experience and your knowledge of other organisations and initiatives, how would you rank the importance of the following criteria?	1	2	3	4	5
Overall impact	24	25	23	25	38
Protection of human rights	79	18	17	14	7
Sustainability	12	38	45	32	8
Transferability	5	19	23	32	56
Intersectoral coordination	15	35	27	32	26

PERCEPTIONS